

Administrative Capacity and Service Quality of Local Governments in Oyo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Anchored on the Dynamic Capability theory, the study assessed the interactions of administrative capacity and service quality of six Local Governments in Oyo State, Nigeria. A mixed method involving qualitative and quantitative data collection was adopted while 384 people from the six selected Local Governments in Oyo State, Nigeria were studied. Multiple linear regression analysis was used to test the hypotheses in the study. The findings revealed that administrative capacity significantly has a positive but weak significant effect on the service quality of selected Local Government areas in Oyo State, Nigeria. The study concluded that the government at the Federal and State levels must appreciate the local government's legislative obligations to the grassroots economy. More so, the local government's capability to deliver the dividend of democracy lies in its administrative and financial autonomy. The study recommended that the leadership of the local government in Oyo State need to provide funds to innovate the local government offices and encourage innovation in terms of policies that can enhance service quality for the citizens of Oyo State, Nigeria.

Keywords: Administrative capacity, service quality, local government authority

Introduction

Local government administration is critical in ensuring the efficient provision of public amenities to large rural populations. Local government is an administrative organization at the local level that promotes decentralization, national integration, governance efficiency, and a sense of belonging. It is a type of administrative entity found worldwide (Majekodunmi, 2021). Many academics believe that the purpose of local governments is to encourage local participation in governance, promote self-government, and encourage people to find solutions to problems in their environment and for their well-being through the formulation and implementation of relevant and adequate policies (Abe and Omotoso, 2014). As a result, the local government must have

the administrative capacity to ensure that the functions for which it was established are carried out. The ability to effectively implement policy plans and programs, in particular, is critical to the success of the grassroots sector. Indeed, having a local government authority capable of optimally aligning resources with actions and implementing designed policies is widely regarded as a critical factor in any State's quality of government and the success of its developmental efforts (Agba, Akwara and Idu, 2017). Effective and rigorous implementation and the ability to deliver on policy promises are key factors that distinguish high-performing local government authorities from those that perform mediocly (Bolaito and Ibrahim, 2016).

In Nigeria's sociopolitical context, with its multiplicity of culture, diversity of languages, and differentiated needs and means, the importance of such an organization in fostering the needed national consciousness, unity, and relative uniformity, as well as preservation of peculiar diversities, cannot be overstated. The Federal Republic of Nigeria's 1999 constitution (as amended) recognizes three administrative and governance divisions at the federal, state, and local government levels. Sections 2 and 3 of the constitution, which lists the number of states and local governments in the federation, refer to Nigeria as one indivisible and indissoluble sovereign state. Section 7 of the constitution states that "the system of democratically elected local government councils is guaranteed under this constitution; and accordingly, the government of every state shall ensure their existence, subject to section 8 of this constitution, by providing for the establishment, structure, composition, finance, and functions of such councils." However, providing services to the people at the grassroots level remains an important component of Nigeria's establishment of this tier of government. Service delivery refers to the provision of social or public goods that benefit citizens' socioeconomic well-being.

Local government, as the lowest and most accessible level of government to citizens, is strategically positioned to serve as an effective tool for development, service delivery, and democratic participation. However, there have been criticisms of the local government over the years that it has not served as a service delivery agent. Poor service delivery, as reflected in poor

service quality, operational efficiency, engagement, poor responsiveness, and bad governance, continues to be a major challenge in most Nigerian local governments. Another source of concern is local government administrative capacity to deliver value to the grassroots economy. Administrative capacity within the political space is the ability to improve the welfare of the governed, and the citizens, by providing appropriate services, and facilitating job creation, schooling, and health care, to name a few. When all public administrative resources are fully utilized, it is the maximum sustainable level of public output. However, Oyo State's local governments have yet to live up to expectations due to weakened administrative capacity caused by a lack of political, financial, and administrative autonomy.

Scholarly writings have been documented to support the importance of administrative capacity, primarily through the qualitative method and an exploratory research approach. These studies have concentrated on organized private and public organizations, financial and administrative reforms, and personnel management issues in research contexts other than those proposed in this study. As a result, empirical discussion on the relationship between administration capacity and service quality of local governments in Oyo State has largely gone unexplored. This gap in the literature limits the broad conceptual, and empirical understanding of administrative capability influences local government service quality in Oyo State. Therefore, the study aims to investigate administrative capacity's effects on service quality at local governments in Oyo State.

Literature Review

Theory and Hypotheses Development

The Dynamic Capability Theory (DCT) is rooted in the need for institutions to possess the knowledge, skill, and abilities (KSA) to survive and thrive in a changing environment. The concept of dynamic capability was conceived by David J. Teece; Gary Pisano; Amy Shuen (Teece *et al.*, 1997). Dynamic capabilities indicate an entity's ability to integrate, create, and reconfigure internal and external capabilities to handle the fast-changing environment (Branden Burger and Stuart, 2018; Samsud and Ismail, 2019). Teece's submission implies that dynamic capabilities enable an institution to respond instinctively to changing and turbulent environments (Christensen, 2020). However, the key assumptions of Dynamic Capability Theory (DCT) are that institutions in the same industry perform differently because they have diverse types of resources and capabilities. The institution's distinctive, scarce, and imitable resources have resulted in competitive advantage and firm expansion. Three, the process of preserving a competitive advantage is both endless and dynamic. Four, in order to remain competitive, the institution must acquire specialized capabilities and engage in continual learning. Finally, a lack of dynamic skills will prevent the firm from maintaining its competitive advantage, particularly in a changing environment (Samsudin and Ismail, 2019).

The relevance of this theory was established in a meta-analysis of dynamic capability literature. Despite the approach emanating from the field of strategy, the underlining assumptions of the dynamic capability now represent a vibrant

theoretical underpinning for several scholarly works in other areas of study such as entrepreneurship, technology and innovation management, international management, operations management, management information systems, and marketing management (Peteraf, 2019).

Despite the limitations and critiques of DCT, the overwhelming support of the theory in recent empirical literature in different disciplines of studies was reinforced by its wide adaptability for diverse study contexts (Teece, 2019). More so, its relevance to this study stemmed from its capability to explain how the local governments in Oyo State, Nigeria, can improve their service delivery within a dynamic environment by deploying administrative capacity such as strategic planning, which lays forth a plan for accomplishing an organization's objectives. Understanding the institutional objectives of a corporate strategic plan will aid in the development of effective plans to guide the growth of the institution (Maleka, 2014). Management control, is the process through which an institution establishes performance objectives and works to attain them as best as possible over time (Giraud *et al.*, 2011), and innovation capability which is the ability to recognize new ideas and develop them into new/improved services. These are not static state administrative capacity. Furthermore, the DCT gave a theoretical justification for the requirement to continually evaluate the external environment and deploy suitable knowledge, skill, and ability to produce a meaningful administrative performance result. The bottom line is that an agency of the government that

aspires to survive and prosper in a fast-changing environment would depend largely on its ability to adapt consistently, sense, and develop its internal resources to align with its surroundings. This is why this research accepts the DCT as relevant for this investigation.

Based on the theory studied, this research takes the dynamic capacity as its foundation theory. The theory explains the interplay between administrative ability and service quality of local government in Oyo State, Nigeria. State capacity must not be static but dynamic so that the local governments and its agencies can adapt and deal with environmental circumstances to generate its residents' desired economic well-being. This study, therefore, tested the following hypothesis.

H₁: The effect of administrative capacity on service quality at the local government level in Oyo State is not significant.

Administrative Capacity and Service Quality

There is an established cross-disciplinary intellectual tradition of researching state capacity, notably in political science and political sociology (Price, 2020). The concept has recently shifted more toward the administrative dimension of state capacity, that is, administrative capacity, which is being widely used in public administration and policy studies (Pugh, Hickson, Hinings, and Turner, 2008). The practical significance of this capacity is highlighted in terms of its necessity for economic performance, industrial growth, policy implementation, and overall national development (Rabey, 2017).

In this globalization era, administrative capacity must be strengthened to cope with the international setting of fierce competition,

complexity, and unpredictability and to successfully confront financial crises, security threats, natural catastrophes, and pandemics (Schoonoven, 2018). In addition, the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development based on the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) provides additional relevance for improving administrative capacity (Scott, 2018). Nonetheless, the basic idea of capacity remains fairly contentious since there are cross-disciplinary variances in its interpretation and its research-driven applications (Woodward, 2020). It has been noted by Whittle and Rafferty (2012) that with the proliferation of models and methodologies, capacity has increasingly become a "contested concept."

On the other hand, the actual attempts made by many nations to improve capacity are not generalizable since these projects or measures are frequently arbitrarily mandated by international organizations (Barney, 2020). It was noted previously that while administrative capacity forms a fundamental aspect of total state capacity, its appropriateness and efficacy are substantially impacted by its historical, political, economic, and socio-cultural circumstances, which differ cross-nationally and cross-regionally.

The competence to successfully execute policy plans and programs is vital to the prosperity of countries. Indeed, having a strong public sector that can best match resources with actions and execute specified policies is generally recognized to be a critical aspect in any state's quality of government and the success of its development efforts (Barney, 2021, Barney and Clark, 2017). No matter how representative

or democratically developed public policies are, it is useless if governments cannot execute them (Bloom and Van, 2021). None of today's key milestones could have been reached without such capabilities, including the deployment of physical and financial resources, long-term planning, implementing innovation, and monitoring performance (Halgesteen and Becker, 2013). Even more so, today's complicated, fast-changing policy climate needs more remarkable efforts. Thus, administrative capacity may be predicted and assessed differently based on the most important or practicable components in a specific context, with some indices and measures concentrating more explicitly on the organizational-operational dimension than others (Hardor, Randiell, Stella, and Barrero, 2018). The relevance of administrative capacity is evident in the national competitive advantage sustained by nations such as Singapore, Denmark, the Netherlands, New Zealand, and Switzerland that embarked on administrative modernization (Hassan and Iwuamadi, 2018). These countries have in common a relatively well-trained, well-paid, autonomous, and capable public service that is responsive, committed, and delivers quality service to their citizens.

Experts suggested that companies with well-crafted strategic plan papers fared better than those that did not have any. By inference, gaining considerable institutional productivity does not happen by luck. Thus, institutions must have a purposeful strategy to attain their aims. Comparable research similarly concluded that strategic planning enhanced, institutional performance (Hoeflich, 2018). The conclusion of the research was verified despite doing their

investigations in a different geographical location (Honey and Okafor, 2018; Hoppe, Van, and Coenen, 2018). It was proven that mid-sized firms in Western Sri Lanka that were marginally employing strategic planning had a considerable increase in operational performance (Ibem, 2019).

In a similar study, statistical results confirm the positive and significant effect of strategic planning and innovation on the organizational performance of the Dubai Police (International Federation of Red Cross, 2015; 2017). Also, a study revealed that strategic planning measures are significant contributors to generating improved firms' success (Jesse, Agrawal, and Larson, 2018).

Another comparative research done in local public institutions averred that external and formal internal control were substantially linked with all three performance aspects - financial, service quality, and procedural, as predicted. However, informal internal control only had a significant association with service quality performance (Pelling and Wosner, 2019). This study also revealed that the external control, through the presence of formal internal control, had a stronger relationship with all three performance dimensions than the direct relationship between the external control and performance. This also aligns with the submission that affirms the relevance of management control to operational efficiency and effective service delivery (Peters, Lanra, Twiggs, and Walch, 2019; Rao, 2018).

H₁: The effect of administrative capacity on service quality of the local government level in Oyo State is not significant.

Figure 1: Conceptual Model
Source: Researchers' Model 2022

Methodology

This research utilized a mixed technique which comprised gathering quantitative data and the use of qualitative data to complement the conclusion produced from the analysis of quantitative data. The mixed method was utilized to determine the effect of administrative ability on the service quality of local governments in Oyo State, Nigeria. In the same vein, a cross-sectional survey research strategy was chosen since it allows for analyzing a subset of a population at the moment in time. More so, researchers consider a cross-sectional survey design ideal since it is cheaper and requires less time compared to a longitudinal study (Hoppe, Van, and Coenen, 2019). This employment is premised on existent studies that found the mixed method approach suitable for a study of this sort (Hoppe, Van, and Coenen, 2019; Onamusi, 2020; Ibem, 2018; Ibronke, 2022).

The population of this research consists of 7,840,864 persons, according to Oyo State Local Government Service Commission. This figure comprises individuals working in the local governments and the citizens. That is political officials, staff workers, and citizens of Oyo State's thirty-three local governments. Given the goal of this research which analyzes political

leadership, administrative ability, and service delivery, the target populations include local government personnel (political and appointed) and the citizens of the local government studied. The rationale for this is to be able to obtain the required input to fulfil the objective of this research.

The sample size of this research is three hundred and eighty-four (384), which is made up of local government workers in the six chosen local governments in Oyo State, Nigeria. The inclusion of the people of the local government's understudy is necessitated by the fact that they are seen as an acceptable data source for service delivery of the local government of residence. The multistage sampling approach was found to be valuable by the researchers because it is adaptable, cost-effective, and enables the researcher to split the general population into smaller groups or sample frames from which primary data may be gathered, analyzed, and conclusions derived. A structured questionnaire in accordance with existing research was prepared and utilized as the instrument of data collection. The structured questionnaire provides a substantial data source that boosted the outcomes of a mixed method study above either quantitative or qualitative research technique.

The researchers spoke with the necessary authorities at the six local governments to obtain permission to perform this study. This technique was essential because of the ethical difficulties in research-related data acquisition. The local government officials' approval significantly ease the process of questionnaire administration, retrieval, and response rate. Considering the sample size and the time period permitted for this study, this researcher engaged six research assistants who aided in the administration, retrieval, and first sorting of the questionnaires. The researcher highlighted the relevance of the study's results (to local government officials and academics) to the research assistants. More so, underlining how scepticism in the questionnaire administration might imperil these conclusions.

Analysis and Results

The questions in this research were acquired via a related literature review and modified from studies that have been utilized and regarded as valid instruments. For criteria and content validity, the instruments were verified by senior faculty members in the Department of Public Administration, Lead City University, Ibadan, and the opinion of practitioners who took part in the pilot study. The inputs were utilized to amend the questionnaire as required for the main research. The researchers put the questionnaires to a reliability test to assess the internal consistency of all items measuring each variable in the study. Internal consistency was utilized to establish the reliability of the replies to the questionnaire elements.

Applicable to multiple-item assessment instruments (like this research), Cronbach's alpha

coefficient is often utilized to determine this internal consistency. A Cronbach's alpha value of > 0.7 but < 1 score for a questionnaire is determined to be trustworthy. The instrument's reliability was done via a pilot study employing 38 copies of the questionnaire, which were given to other local government workers not part of the research. The outcome of the reliability test demonstrates that Cronbach Alpha's coefficient of 0.79, 0.81, and 0.760 argues that the instrument is dependable for the primary research.

The researchers evaluated the data acquired (after completing numerous data treatments) using descriptive, inferential statistics and content analysis. Concerning inferential statistics, this research employs a partial least square structural equation modeling as the analytical approach to assess the hypotheses made for this study. The outcome of the hypothesis tested is significant at a probability value of less than 0.05. The descriptive statistics were done using Statistical Package for Service Solutions (SPSS) version 25. The inferential statistics were done using Smart PLS version 3.3.5 since it is an acceptable statistical platform that permits primary data (questionnaire) to be analysed. It is vital to highlight that the interview results were utilized to give further support for the conclusions of the qualitative analysis.

A total of three hundred and eighty-four (384) copies of the questionnaire were administered to the personnel of the local government and the population separately. For the local government, three hundred and ten (310) copies were obtained. After sorting the questionnaires, two hundred and thirty-two

(232) copies were validated as properly completed and declared useful. For the local government people, three hundred and ten (323) copies were obtained. After sorting the questionnaires, two hundred and thirty-two (257) copies were validated as properly completed and declared useful. The usable questionnaire indicated a 60.41 percent and 66.92 percent response rate for local government officials and their residents accordingly.

Test of Hypothesis

H₁: Administrative capacity has no significant effect on the service quality of selected local government areas in Oyo State, Nigeria.

To test the null hypothesis, Partial Least Square-Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) was adopted using the Smart PLS statistical platform

version 3.3.5. The study used the PLS-algorithm's command, which is appropriate for predicting impact, ran the bootstrapping to ascertain the level of significant of the prediction, and ran blindfolding to confirm the predictive relevance of the model. The choice of PLS-SEM (via Smart PLS) is because it is a more advanced multivariate analytical technique which offers stricter and robust analysis compared with the outcomes of SPSS.

Data from two hundred and thirty-two (232) respondents were collated for the analysis. The result of the PLS-SEM is presented in three models. Figure 2 shows the path analysis while Figure 3 shows the t value which confirms the significance of the path analysis and Figure 4 shows the Q² which established the predictive relevance of the structural model. Table 1 provides a tabular summary of the information.

Figure 2: Path Analysis for Hypothesis Two

Source: Researchers' Computation via Smart PLS V 3.3.5

Figure 3: T-Statistics for Hypothesis Two

Source: Researchers' Computation via Smart PLS V 3 .3.5

Figure 4: Q² Statistics for Hypothesis Two

Source: Researchers' Computation via Smart PLS V 3.3.5

Table 1: Summary of the effect of Administrative Capacity on Service Quality of selected local government in Oyo State, Nigeria using PLS-SEM

Path Description	Original sample(o)						
	Unstandardized Beta	t	Sig.	R ²	Adj. R ²	Sig.	Q ²
Innovation capability Service quality	0.005	0.040	0.968				
Management control Service quality	0.251	2.058	0.040	0.319	0.297	0.000	0.100
Strategy planning Service quality	0.374	2.682	0.008				

Dependent Variable: Service quality,

Predictors: Innovation capability, Management control and Strategy planning.

Source: Researchers' Result via Smart PLS Version 3.3.5 (2022).

Figures 2, 3, and 4 present the results of PLS-SEM analysis for the effect of administrative capacity on service quality of selected local governments in Oyo State, Nigeria, using PLS-SEM. The Adjusted R² was used to establish the predictive power of the study's model. From the results, the adjusted coefficient of determination (*Adj R²*) of 0.297 shows that administrative capacity explained 29.7% of the changes experienced in service quality of selected local government in Oyo State while the remaining 70.3% variation in service quality is attributable to other exogenous factors different from the administrative capacity factors considered in this study and the effect is statistically significant at 95% confidence interval.

The path coefficient of each administrative capacity sub-measures (innovation capability, Management control and Strategy planning) represents the coefficient of determination (β)

which shows the relative influence of each administrative capacity sub-measures on service quality of the selected local government in Oyo State. The PLS-SEM results in Figures 2, 3, and 4 revealed that at 95% confidence level, management control ($\beta=0.251$, $t=2.058$) and strategy planning ($\beta=0.374$, $t= 2.682$) are significant; however, innovation capability ($\beta = 0.005$, $t=0.040$) is statistically insignificant.

This result shows that the relative influence of management control and strategic planning and its corresponding t-value are greater than the threshold of 1.96, suggesting a statistically significant relative influence. However, the relative effect of innovation capability has t-values below the acceptable threshold of 1.96 to suggest that the relative effect is statistically insignificant. The result also indicates that taking all other independent variables at zero, a unit change in management control will lead to a

0.251 increase in service quality in selected local government in Oyo State, given that all other factors are held constant. Also, taking all other independent variables at zero, a unit change in strategy planning will lead to a 0.374 increase in service quality in selected local government in Oyo State given that all other factors are held constant. Overall, strategy planning ($\beta = 0.381$) has the highest relative influence, followed by management control ($\beta = 0.337$). Given the PLS-SEM predictive results in Table 2 ($Adj R^2 = 0.297$; $p = 0.000$, $Q^2 = 0.100$), this study can conclude that administrative capacity has a positive and significant effect on service quality in selected local governments in Oyo State, Nigeria. Hence, the study rejects the null hypothesis one (H_0) which states that administrative capacity has no significant effect on the service quality of selected local government areas in Oyo State, Nigeria.

Discussion, Conclusion and Recommendations

The findings of multiple regression analysis on the effect of administrative capacity on the service quality of local governments in Oyo State, Nigeria, found that administrative capacity has a positive and substantial effect on service delivery. Conceptually, the existence of internal organisational capacity such as strategic planning, innovation capability, and managerial control are contextualized as administrative capacity success criteria for local government. This conclusion corresponds with this study's premise about administrative competence. This research evaluated administrative capacity from the dynamic capability theory, which emphasized that administrative capacity is an intangible asset that

local government may grow through time and deploy to achieve improved social performance in a changing environment.

From the theoretical standpoint, both the dynamic capability theory is enhanced. The dynamic capability theory in an inside-out viewpoint, highlights that for company to attain exceptional performance, such businesses must possess internal organisational knowledge, skill, and ability that are highly distinctive. Furthermore, the dynamic capability theory emphasizes the necessity for a business to guarantee it has internal and external organization abilities one that adjust to changing environments as a prerequisite to obtaining better performance. This study's findings are in concomitance with these theoretical approaches. Therefore, on the basis of the support discovered in conceptual, empirical and theoretical contributions in current literature with this present research's outcome, the study contends that administrative capacity has considerable influence on new product performance.

This study was carried out to examine administrative capacity (strategic planning, innovation capability, and management control) on service delivery (operational efficiency, service quality, and responsiveness) of six local governments area in Oyo State with rural and urban representation. However, underpinning the result demonstrates that all the elements of administrative capability had a minimal contribution to the service quality in the local governments analyzed in Oyo State. This is a cause of worry for the local government administration if it wishes to accomplish

considerable development and compete with global public service performance standards.

The results of this research have significant relevance for the government regarding the administration of the local government and the subsequent contribution to the grassroots economy. It is vital that government at the Federal and State levels realize the statutory responsibility of the local government to the grassroots economy more so that the local government's competence to provide the dividend of democracy lays its political, administrative, and financial autonomy. Village needs vary from one community to another, even under similar municipal authority. Hence, the assumption that the State government governs the local government is detrimental to their potential to become the mainstay of the local economy and supply vital infrastructure developmental amenities to the grassroots economy.

Based on the outcomes of this investigation, the following suggestions are given; underlining the significant influence of administrative capacity on service quality of selected local governments in Oyo State is an insignificant relative effect of innovation capability. Hence, the leadership of the local government in Oyo State should ensure it acquires and train its staff on information communication technology equipment; more so, Oyo State government needs to provide funds to innovate the local government offices and encourage innovation in term of policies that can enhance service quality for the citizens of Oyo State, Nigeria.

This work makes a substantial addition to literature philosophically, theoretically, and

practically. Based on the conceptual evaluation done, this work makes deep addition to knowledge conceptually innumerable aspects. The research identified and addressed conceptual gaps in literature surrounding the administrative ability, and service quality of local government in Oyo State, Nigeria. Another conceptual addition to knowledge were the administrative capability sub-variables utilized in this research. Hence, future research may employ the semetrics to increase its generalizability. In conclusion, the conceptual model produced for the research highlights another area in which this study has added to the knowledge conceptually since no known comparable studies, both theoretical and empirical, have employed the model in their investigations. Hence, contributes to theories that might explain the relationship between political leadership, administrative ability, and service performance.

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